

EDITING FASHION IMAGES WITH PRECISION: A CONTROLLED IN PAINTING METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Text-guided image editing, especially in the fashion domain, is a powerful yet complex task that involves modifying specific elements of an image based solely on textual instruction. The system must not only interpret the instruction but also localize and edit the relevant image regions while preserving the rest of the visual content. In this article, we present a practical and controlled methodology for generating a paired dataset to support this task. Our approach builds on recent advancements in generative AI, combining Stable Diffusion inpainting techniques with pre-trained large language models to produce consistent and faithful edits. Specifically, we leverage human parsing and fashion-specific datasets to enable localized garment transformations based on color and fabric changes. This article complements the work presented in our paper "AI-Powered Text-Guided Image Editing: Innovations in Fashion and Beyond", presented at the ISPR 2025 conference, by providing a focused exploration of the dataset generation pipeline and implementation details used in that study.

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, Computer Vision, Image Editing, Neural Models, Text-Guided Image Editing, Deep Learning, Large Language Models (LLMs).

1. INTRODUCTION

The integration of textual guidance into image editing tasks has become a major focus of computer vision research in today's digital age. The ability to interpret and execute image edits based on textual instructions represents a groundbreaking approach with wide ranging applications, from creative content generation to image enhancement in various domains [4]. The ability to edit images using natural language instructions not only simplifies the user experience but also enhances the precision and scalability of visual content modification. In this work, we focus on developing a text-guided image editing system specifically tailored for fashion images, covering both realistic images sourced from catalogs or photographs, and AI-generated images. Unlike general-purpose editing, fashion-specific editing demands meticulous attention to detail to preserve garment identity, texture, and style while performing modifications such as changing colors or fabrics. Our objective is to build a system capable of modifying fashion images based solely on user-provided textual instructions. This approach eliminates the need for complex manual editing tools, making image editing more accessible and intuitive.

Text-to-image diffusion models have become state-of-the-art tools in generative image synthesis. Models such as DALL·E 2 [14] and Imagen [3] have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in producing high-fidelity images from textual prompts. However, these models often fall short when precise control is required, particularly for localized changes or when dealing

with realistic image inputs. They may struggle to preserve original content or interpret fine-grained user intent.

On the other hand, attribute-based editing techniques such as ControlNet [18, 19] enable more controlled modifications, for example, adjusting the color of a garment or changing the style of footwear based on text. Yet, these approaches are typically limited to predefined attributes and may inadvertently alter important garment features during complex edits. Similarly, object-level editing methods like SDEdit and DiffEdit [5] facilitate the addition or transformation of objects within an image but often rely on user-defined masks or inversion techniques, which may reduce the precision and controllability of the results. Spatial manipulation methods such as DragGAN [11] excel at moving objects within an image but are not designed to handle stylistic or semantic modifications such as color or fabric changes.

Despite these advancements, several critical challenges remain. Many existing solutions rely on optimization-based methods that are computationally expensive and lack scalability due to the need for per-prompt or per-image tuning. Moreover, a fundamental requirement in image editing—preserving unedited regions while applying accurate changes to specific areas—is often inadequately addressed. This can result in unintended alterations that compromise the quality and integrity of the final image. A major limitation of current generative methods lies in their poor adaptability to realistic images, which are inherently more complex than synthetic ones. Realistic fashion photography requires editing solutions that maintain garment texture, fit, and aesthetic consistency—criteria that many models trained on synthetic datasets fail to meet. Compounding this challenge, a lack of suitable datasets for training text-guided fashion image editing systems necessitated the development of custom data generation approaches. To address the absence of a pre-existing dataset, we employed two novel approaches to generate the required training data. The first approach draws inspiration from the InstructPix2Pix [4] framework, where textual instructions were paired with corresponding edited images generated through iterative refinement. The second approach, based on our own research, leverages large language models (LLMs) to generate diverse and meaningful textual instructions. These instructions were then paired with images edited using Stable Diffusion models to simulate the desired outcomes. This dual strategy allowed us to construct a comprehensive dataset encompassing a wide range of editing scenarios, tailored specifically for the fashion domain.

In this work, we introduce a novel text-guided image editing system designed specifically for fashion images. Our system bridges the gap between generated and realistic inputs by enabling precise, high-fidelity edits based on textual instructions. Built upon the Stable Diffusion architecture and enhanced by instruction-tuned LLMs, our framework preserves the visual integrity of garments while ensuring consistency with user intent. We address both technical challenges and dataset limitations, presenting a scalable and robust solution to text-based image editing in fashion.

This article is organized as follows: we begin by detailing the business and research context, followed by a thorough description of our dataset generation pipeline. We then explain the architecture and optimization strategies of our proposed system, and finally, we present experimental results highlighting the effectiveness of our approach in comparison with existing methods.

2. BACKGROUND

The key feature of transformer-based architecture is the attention mechanism, which captures intricate dependencies within input and output sequences. This innovation has been pivotal in adapting these models for multimodal tasks such as text-guided image editing, enabling them to

revolutionize not only natural language processing (NLP) [1,15] but also image generation and editing by effectively bridging textual and visual modalities. Although traditional attention mechanisms were combined with recurrent networks to improve sequence modeling [10]. However, this approach poses challenges, particularly regarding computational efficiency and handling long dependencies. The transformer model emerges as a state-of-the-art solution in the realm of NLP, specifically designed to address these challenges. This innovative approach revolutionizes the field of NLP, offering unparalleled efficiency and effectiveness in capturing intricate relationships within sequences. It aims to revolutionize image editing by offering a user-friendly alternative to complex editing tools. By enabling users to articulate desired modifications through instructions, we aim to streamline the editing process significantly.

Over recent years, generative models have advanced to produce high-quality synthetic images by employing techniques such as Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPM) [6]. These models simulate a diffusion process where noise is progressively added to an image and then systematically removed, allowing for the reconstruction of clear, realistic images and the generation of new visuals that reflect patterns from the training data.

Diffusion models have become pivotal in image editing applications [16, 17], excelling in tasks such as denoising, in painting, super-resolution, and style transfer [2, 8]. Their adaptability makes them particularly suitable for integrating textual conditions as guidance, enabling intuitive user interaction through simple text inputs. By eliminating the need for expertise in traditional editing tools, text-based guidance opens up accessibility to a wider audience. Although these methods show promise in image editing, they often struggle with synthesizing image information and targeted editing tasks due to gaps between image modalities and the limited context provided by textual inputs. Text-based instructions usually do not convey the full context of the image, which makes it difficult to accurately determine the key elements that need to be changed. Consequently, the edits might not align with the user's expectations.

To overcome these challenges, additional guidance techniques have been explored. One common approach is to incorporate manual annotations, such as masks, to explicitly mark the regions of an image to be edited [12]. This method enhances precision by directing the model to focus on specific areas based on user-customized instructions. While effective, the reliance on manual annotations limits scalability and reduces the general applicability of text-guided systems for large-scale or automated editing tasks.

The emergence of multimodal learning models such as CLIP Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training [13] represents a significant advancement in the field. CLIP, a neural network developed by OpenAI, is designed to learn visual concepts from language descriptions. It addresses the challenge of learning visual representation from natural language by adapting a contrastive learning approach. Its strength lies in its ability to leverage a diverse and expansive dataset of both images and text. Contrastive learning, a widely used technique in machine learning, particularly in unsupervised learning, focuses on training AI models to identify similarities and differences across various data points. Our objective focuses on building a system that can effectively edit images based on user-provided textual instruction. We used a pre-trained model that can understand these instructions and use them to edit the image. To enhance the system's performance for our specific needs, we finetuned the model using a collection of text instructions along with their corresponding original and edited images. This helped the system work faster and more accurately; while also making sure it understands the instructions we give it.

3. DATA AND METHODS

Developing an innovative image editing system driven by textual instructions requires not only

advanced models but also a robust and representative dataset. Such a dataset must effectively bridge the gap between natural language directives and the desired visual modifications, especially in the domain of fashion imagery. However, existing datasets tailored for this specific task are scarce, posing a significant challenge. To overcome this, we devised two complementary approaches for generating a dataset specifically tailored to our use case. These approaches were informed by extensive research in the field and were designed to balance realism, diversity, and relevance to fashion image editing.

3.1. Approach 1: Following the InstructPix2Pix Framework

This approach is inspired by the InstructPix2Pix framework, which proposes an efficient way to create a training dataset for image editing by pairing an original image, a modified version of it, and a corresponding textual instruction. This is achieved using large language models (LLMs) and diffusion-based image generation models.

In our implementation, we applied this framework to the FashionGen dataset and adapted it to fashion-specific use cases using the Falcon 7B language model and a pre-trained Stable Diffusion model. Our goal was to generate a high-quality training dataset tailored to text-guided fashion image editing.

Step 1: Preprocessing the FashionGen Dataset: The Fashion-Gen dataset

is a large-scale dataset containing high-resolution fashion images (1360×1360 pixels) with detailed textual descriptions written by professional stylists. This dataset is widely used in fashion image generation, retrieval, and text-guided modifications.

The dataset consists of 293,008 fashion images, each captured from multiple angles (e.g., front pose, full pose). These images are paired with textual attributes describing the clothing's category, style, material, and color. We focused only on specific poses, namely the front and full poses, to standardize the data and facilitate meaningful comparisons. Each image's description was then enriched using structured concatenation of the metadata. This preprocessing ensures that the input to the language model is both rich in context and standardized in structure, enabling better instruction generation downstream:

	pose	description	gender	sub_category	category	final_description
0	b'front pose'	b'Long sleeve coated denim shirt in indigo blu...	b'Men'	b'SHIRTS'	shirts	b'front pose of SHIRTS for Men. Long sleeve co...
1	b'full pose'	b'Long sleeve coated denim shirt in indigo blu...	b'Men'	b'SHIRTS'	shirts	b'full pose of SHIRTS for Men. Long sleeve coa...
2	b'front pose'	b'Long sleeve sweatshirt in heather grey. Band...	b'Women'	b'HOODIES & ZIPUPS'	sweaters	b'front pose of HOODIES & ZIPUPS for Women. Lo...
3	b'full pose'	b'Long sleeve sweatshirt in heather grey. Band...	b'Women'	b'HOODIES & ZIPUPS'	sweaters	b'full pose of HOODIES & ZIPUPS for Women. Lon...
4	b'front pose'	b'Skinny-fit jeans in indigo. Turquoise overdy...	b'Women'	b'JEANS'	jeans	b'front pose of JEANS for Women. Skinny-fit jea...
5	b'full pose'	b'Skinny-fit jeans in indigo. Turquoise overdy...	b'Women'	b'JEANS'	jeans	b'full pose of JEANS for Women. Skinny-fit jea...
6	b'front pose'	b'Long sleeve flannel plaid shirt in tones of ...	b'Men'	b'SHIRTS'	shirts	b'front pose of SHIRTS for Men. Long sleeve fl...
7	b'full pose'	b'Long sleeve flannel plaid shirt in tones of ...	b'Men'	b'SHIRTS'	shirts	b'full pose of SHIRTS for Men. Long sleeve fla...

Fig. 1. Sample Data from the Fashion-Gen Data

Step 2: Instruction and Edited Description Generation using Falcon 7B

Once the original captions were preprocessed, the Falcon 7B model was used to generate two textual elements:

- A textual instruction (e.g., "Change the fabric to velvet and make it blue.")
 - A new caption (i.e., a rephrased version of the original caption based on the modification described in the instruction). To do this effectively, we designed a prompt template that was optimized through several trials. The model's generation was fine-tuned using the following parameters:

Table 1. Text Generation Parameters and Objectives

Parameters	Purpose
temperature = 0.1	Controls randomness in generation; a low value ensures focused and deterministic output.
top-k = 10	Limits sampling to the top 10 probable tokens to maintain coherence.
top-p = 0.9	Enables nucleus sampling, considering tokens whose cumulative probability is below 0.9.
no-repeat-ngram-size = 3	Prevents repetition by avoiding any 3-gram repetition in the output.
repetition-penalty = 2.0	Penalizes repeated tokens to encourage diversity.
max_length = 800	Sets the maximum length of generated text to maintain relevance and control verbosity.
num_return_sequences = 1	Limits output to a single instruction per generation round.

To ensure the quality of the generated instructions, we calculated cosine similarity scores between the input description and each candidate instruction and selected the top 3 most semantically relevant instructions.

Step 3: Image Generation using Stable Diffusion

Once we had the original description and the modified description, we used a pre-trained Stable Diffusion model to generate both the edited and original image. The diffusion model was conditioned on the modified caption to produce a new image that reflects the required visual changes, while maintaining most of the original content. Each entry in the dataset then became a triplet: Original Image, Edited Image and Instruction. This approach allowed us to automatically create a large dataset of instruction-based fashion image edits with paired examples for supervised training.

The overall workflow for this approach is summarized in Figure 2, which outlines the step by-step process to generate high-quality paired data for training.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the first approach

Limitations of Approach 1

Despite implementing the same technique as the InstructPix2Pix paper, the results were still not as desired. The image generated from the modified description often failed faithfulness to the original image. While this approach offered a scalable method for generating a large dataset, it presented certain limitations in our case:

- Ambiguity in Instruction Generation: Falcon 7B often produces general or vague instructions, making precise modifications difficult.
- Inconsistency in Image Edits: The Stable Diffusion model lacks fine control over localized edits, sometimes introducing unintended changes that distort the original image.
- Challenges with Realistic Edits: Due to the diverse nature of the Fashion-Gen dataset, maintaining consistency between edited and original images is difficult, especially when handling fine-grained modifications such as fabric texture or subtle color variations.

These limitations reduce the reliability of the dataset for training high-quality models. To overcome these issues, we developed a second approach that ensures better precision and control over the editing process.

3.2. Approach 2: Controlled Edits Using an Inpainting Model

Here, we explored and proposed an approach for generating the dataset. The goal of this new method is to ensure that the generated images for the original and modified descriptions maintain a more faithful visual relationship. To achieve this, we utilized a pre-trained Stable Diffusion inpainting model [9], which allows for more controlled and precise edits to specific regions of an image based on given masks. This approach leverages Human-parsing-dataset and Fashion-controlnet-dataset from HuggingFace [7], which includes images, masks, and Captions: Human-parsing-dataset typically contains labeled images in which each pixel is annotated to correspond to a specific category, such as body parts (e.g., head, arms, legs), clothing (e.g., shirts, pants), or accessories. This dataset is used in tasks like person segmentation and human part recognition to enable more detailed image understanding. The Fashion ControlNet Dataset is designed for fashion image generation and manipulation tasks. It includes fashion images annotated with segmentation maps, and other attributes that allow models to generate or edit fashion images based on input prompts. The dataset facilitates advanced applications in fashion image synthesis.

By using the inpainting model, we can focus on making localized edits that are directly related to the modified descriptions, ensuring that the rest of the image remains visually consistent with the original. In this section, we provide a detailed explanation of the code of the initiative approach used for data generation.

Masks and Inpainting Model

For the mask-guided inpainting, we leveraged two rich datasets from HuggingFace: the Human-Parsing Dataset and the Fashion ControlNet Dataset. These datasets were essential for guiding the edits with high precision:

- **Human-Parsing Dataset:** This dataset provides pixel-level annotations for body parts and garments. Each image is segmented into semantic categories such as arms, legs, shirts, and accessories. These fine-grained segmentations allow us to generate accurate binary masks targeting only the garment to be edited.
- **Fashion ControlNet Dataset:** This dataset contains fashion images with associated segmentation maps and attributes. It is specifically designed to support image generation and editing in fashion contexts. We used its annotations and segmentation maps to extract garments more effectively and ensure the edits are contextually consistent.

These segmentation maps were converted into binary masks, where white regions indicate the parts to be edited (e.g., a shirt) and black regions preserve the original content. This ensures that modifications affect only the intended area.

The mask is a crucial input for the inpainting model, guiding which parts of an image should be edited. The model utilizes these masks to accurately target specific garments or body parts for editing. By employing a pre-trained stable diffusion inpainting model, the system can perform localized edits without generating a new image from scratch. This approach ensures that modifications integrate seamlessly with the original image, preserving visual consistency by maintaining the structure and appearance of unchanged areas. Overall, this method allows for precise adjustments while keeping the integrity of the image intact.

Labeling the Dataset

To facilitate controlled edits, we first identified the target garments mentioned in each caption. This was done using a predefined list of garment types. The following code snippet shows how garments were detected from captions and labeled in a new column. (For implementation details, see Appendix A – Code A.1 5)

Identifies and handles rows with missing garment detection, it is then removed from the modified dataset but resets the original image-index after dropping them.

Instruction Generation

Next, we automatically generated text-based editing instructions using a list of predefined colors and fabrics. For each detected garment, a random instruction template was chosen to encourage diversity while maintaining structure. `Pil-to-bytes` is a function to convert a PIL image object into byte data, which is used for saving the image in the specific format (PNG). 2. The example below shows how color modification instructions were generated. (For implementation details, see Appendix A – Code A.2 5)

We apply the same logic for the fabric changes, where the function selects from a predefined fabric list and constructs instructions.

Image Generation Process

For the image generation process, we used the inference of the pre-trained inpainting model GraydientPlatformAPI/jux-inpainting-sdxl, the input to this model included:

- The original image.
- The binary mask indicating the garment region.
- The textual instruction (e.g., “Change the color of the shirt to red”).

After apply this model on the human-parsing-dataset and Fashion-controlnet-dataset, we filtered the results to get a set of 3005 high-quality images. The resulting dataset contains original images, edited images, and the desired instructions.

This approach was designed to address a critical shortcoming in the previous method: faithfulness to the original image. In models like InstructPix2Pix, modifying a textual description often results in images that significantly deviate from the original due to hallucinated artifacts, exaggerated changes, or complete reconstructions.

In contrast, the inpainting strategy introduces controlled, semantically aligned, and visually minimal edits. This makes the dataset particularly suitable for training or evaluating models that require fine-grained, instruction-based modifications with high fidelity to the source image. Fig.3 illustrates the complete pipeline of this approach.

3.3. Fine-tuning Experiments

We explored the fine-tuning experiments conducted on InstructPix2Pix using our generated dataset to enhance its text-guided fashion image editing [4]. Utilizing the Freezing method for fine-tuning, we adapted the model to apply precise modifications. By freezing most of the model’s layers and training only a subset of parameters, we ensured efficient fine-tuning with minimal resource usage.

Fig. 3. Diagram of the second approach

During fine-tuning the InstructPix2Pix model, several arguments are used to control the training process: The model processes 16 samples before updates; the number of samples used during the validation process at each step is equal to 4; the models iterate the entire dataset 50 times during training; the use of the 8-bit Adam optimizer, which reduces memory usage by quantizing Adam's weights to 8-bit precision.

Additionally, to monitor the fine-tuning process, we integrated Weights and Biases (WandB) to track key training metrics in real time. This platform detailed insights into the model's performance, including loss curves, parameter updates, and relevant metrics, ensuring we could adjust the training process for optimal results. (For implementation details, see Appendix A – Code A.3 5)

There are two distinct approaches to fine-tuning the InstructPix2Pix. Both strategies aim to improve the models' ability to generate concise images, but they differ in their methodology. Additionally, we will apply these approaches using 95% of the data for the training and 5% for the validation. The freezing methodology is a widely used technique in finetuning, which involves locking specific layers of the model to prevent their weights from being updated during training. This approach enhances the efficiency of the finetuning process and helps reduce the risk of overfitting.

To better illustrate the dataset distribution and fine-tuning results, we present Table 2, which outlines the number of samples used for training and validation, along with the average SSIM scores achieved during training and testing.

Table 2. Dataset Distribution and SSIM Scores for Fine-Tuning

Dataset Split	Total Samples	Percentage	SSIM (Training Avg.)	SSIM (Testing Avg.)
Training Set	2855	95%	0.87	-
Validation Set	150	5%	-	0.89

Bitsandbytes is a popular approach and library for optimizing model fine-tuning, particularly when using large models. It focuses on reducing the memory footprint of models by utilizing 8-bit and 4-bit precision rather than the usual 16-bit or 32-bit of precision. This allows users to fine-tune large models even on hardware with limited memory, such as GPUs or multi-GPU setups.

3.4. Evaluation

In this part, we evaluate the performance of our model using the Structured Similarity Index Measure (SSIM), which is a metric used to evaluate the quality of images by comparing the structural information between the original edited image (the edited image in the dataset) and the generated image during the training process. It is designed to assess image quality based on three key factors: Luminance measures the brightness of the images; Contrast measures the contrast in intensity; Structure measures the spatial arrangement of pixels. The SSIM index produces values ranging from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates perfect structural similarity between the two images compared. The SSIM index is defined in Eq. (1):

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)} \quad (1)$$

where μ_x and μ_y are the mean values of the two images x and y ; σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 are the variances of the images x and y ; σ_{xy} refers to the covariance between the two images; $C1 = (K1L)^2$ and $C2 = (K2L)^2$ are constants to stabilize the division with small denominators, where L is the dynamic range of the pixel values (typically 255 for 8-bit images), and $K1$ and $K2$ are small constants (often set to 0.01 and 0.03, respectively).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Starting with a lower value around 0.75, the model quickly learns and improves over the first few thousand steps (see Fig. 4). By the end of the training, the SSIM approaches 0.9, indicating that the model has achieved high structural similarity between its outputs and the target images. The validation SSIM curve exhibits a similar trend to the training SSIM curve, serving as a strong indication that the model generalizes effectively to unseen data. Starting near 0.76, the score increases rapidly in the early training phases and continues to improve steadily. By the end of training, the validation SSIM also approaches 0.9, showing that the model maintains high performance on the validation set, avoiding overfitting. This parallel movement between training and validation SSIM curves suggests balanced learning and a robust model.

Our study presents a significant advancement in text-guided image editing within the fashion domain. The high Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) scores, approaching 0.9, indicate that our model effectively maintains the structural integrity of the original images while applying precise edits based on textual instructions. This demonstrates the model's capability to understand and implement user intentions, which is crucial for applications requiring detailed and accurate image modifications.

Compared to existing models like InstructPix2Pix and Stable Diffusion, our approach addresses key challenges identified in prior research. InstructPix2Pix [4], while innovative, struggled with maintaining image consistency and specificity in instruction interpretation, especially with realistic images. Similarly, Stable Diffusion models often lacked precise control over localized edits, leading to unintended changes. Our method, leveraging controlled inpainting techniques and fine-tuning with a custom dataset, provides enhanced precision and consistency. This aligns with recent advancements in diffusion models that emphasize conditional control for improved editing fidelity [18].

Fig. 4. Training and validation SSIM curve

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a comprehensive system for text-guided image editing, with a particular focus on modifying garment color and fabric while maintaining the visual coherence of the original image. Our approach demonstrates strong performance in executing fine-grained, localized edits, especially when modifying individual elements within fashion images. However, the current version of our system exhibits some limitations, most notably in fabric editing, where alterations may occasionally lead to unintended changes in color. Addressing this issue will be a key direction for future work to enhance the accuracy and reliability of our editing process.

Looking ahead, expanding the system's capabilities to support more complex editing tasks, such as the addition or removal of objects, will significantly broaden its applicability. Such advancements would enable more flexible and creative interactions, aligning better with real-world user expectations and workflows.

Beyond its technical contributions, this work provides a scalable and adaptable foundation for further innovations in the field of text-based image editing. The methodologies introduced can be refined and extended to accommodate large-scale, user-driven transformations, ultimately enhancing both the creative potential and usability of intelligent image editing systems in fashion and beyond.

REFERENCES

- [1] Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., Kaiser, L., and Polosukhin, I. (2017). Attention is all you need. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (Vol. 30). DOI: 10.5555/3295222.3295349.
- [2] Avrahami, O., Lischinski, D., and Fried, O. (2022). Blended diffusion for text-driven editing of natural images. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 18208-18218). DOI: 10.1109/CVPR52688.2022.01767.
- [3] Baldridge, J., Bauer, J., Bhutani, M., Brichtova, N., Bunner, A., Chan, K., et al. (2024). Imagen 3. CoRR. arXiv:2408.07009.
- [4] Brooks, T., Holynski, A., and Efros, A. A. (2023). Instructpix2pix: Learning to follow image editing instructions. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (pp. 18392-18402). DOI: 10.1109/CVPR52688.2023.01839.
- [5] Couairon, G., Verbeek, J., Schwenk, H., and Cord, M. (2023, May). DiffEdit: Diffusion-based Semantic Image Editing with Mask Guidance. In *11th International Conference on Learning Representations*. DOI: 10.1109/ICLR.2023.00001.
- [6] Ho, J., Jain, A., and Abbeel, P. (2020). Denoising diffusion probabilistic models. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 33, (pp. 6840-6851). DOI: 10.5555/3454287.3454870.
- [7] Jain, S. M. (2022). Hugging face. In *Introduction to transformers for NLP: With the hugging face library and models to solve problems* (pp. 51-67). Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4842-8844-3_2.
- [8] Kwar, B., Zada, S., et al. (2023). Imagic: Text-based real image editing with diffusion models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (pp. 6007-6017). DOI: 10.1109/CVPR52688.2023.00607.
- [9] Lugmayr, A., Danelljan, M., Romero, A., Yu, F., Timofte, R., and Van Gool, L. (2022). Repaint: Inpainting using denoising diffusion probabilistic models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 11461-11471). DOI: 10.1109/CVPR52688.2022.01117.
- [10] Niu, Z., Zhong, G., and Yu, H. (2021). A review on the attention mechanism of deep learning. *Neurocomputing*, 452, 48-62. DOI: 10.1016/j.neucom.2021.03.091.
- [11] Pan, X., Tewari, A., Leimkühler, T., Liu, L., Meka, A., and Theobalt, C. (2023, July). Drag your gan: Interactive point-based manipulation on the generative image manifold. In *ACM SIGGRAPH 2023 Conference Proceedings* (pp. 1-11). DOI: 10.1145/3588432.3591500.

- [12] Patashnik, O., Garibi, D., Azuri, I., Averbuch-Elor, H., and Cohen-Or, D. (2023). Localizing object-level shape variations with text-to-image diffusion models. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 23051-23061). DOI: 10.1109/ICCV51070.2023.02107.
- [13] Radford, A., Kim, J. W., et al. (2021). Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision. In International conference on machine learning (pp. 8748-8763). PMLR. DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.2103.00020.
- [14] Reddy, M. D. M., Basha, M. S. M., Hari, M. M. C., and Penchalaiah, M. N. (2021). Dall-e: Creating images from text. UGC Care Group I Journal, 8(14), 71-75. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5790549.
- [15] Rivas, P., and Zhao, L. (2024). Marketing and AI-Based Image Generation: A Responsible AI Perspective. In International Conference on Information and Communication Technology for Intelligent Systems (pp. 141-151). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore. DOI: 10.1007/978-981-97-5810-4_13.
- [16] Rombach, R., Blattmann, A., Lorenz, D., Esser, P., and Ommer, B. (2022). High-resolution image synthesis with latent diffusion models. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (pp. 10684-10695). DOI: 10.1109/CVPR52688.2022.01042.
- [17] Song, J., Meng, C., and Ermon, S. (2021). Denoising Diffusion Implicit Models. In International Conference on Learning Representations. DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.2010.02502.
- [18] Zhang, L., Rao, A., and Agrawala, M. (2023). Adding conditional control to text-to-image diffusion models. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 3836-3847). DOI: 10.1109/ICCV56361.2023.00384.
- [19] Zavadski, D., Feiden, J. F., and Rother, C. (2025). ControlNet-XS: Rethinking the Control of Text-to-Image Diffusion Models as Feedback-Control Systems. In European Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 343-362). Springer, Cham.

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APPENDIX

Code A.1 – Detecting the clothing item

```
1 modified_dataset = pandas.DataFrame({'CLIP_captions': dataset['  
    CLIP_captions']})  
2  
3 def detect_garments_in_caption(caption, garments):  
4     for garment in garments:  
5         if garment in caption.lower():  
6             return garment  
7     return None  
8  
9 modified_dataset['detected_garment'] = modified_dataset['CLIP_captions'].  
    apply(lambda caption: detect_garments_in_caption(caption, garments)  
10 )
```

Code A.2 – Random Instruction Generator for Color Changes

```
1 color_names = ['Red', 'Orange', 'Yellow', 'Green', 'Blue', 'Purple', 'Pink'  
    ]  
2 def get_instruction_format(label, selected_color):  
3     formats = [  
4         f"Change the color of {label} to {selected_color}.",  
5         f"Replace the {label} color with {selected_color}.",  
6         f"Make the color of {label} into {selected_color}.",  
7     ]  
8     return random.choice(formats)  
9  
10 def pil_to_bytes(img):  
11     img_byte_arr = io.BytesIO()  
12     img.save(img_byte_arr, format='PNG')  
13     img_byte_arr = img_byte_arr.getvalue()  
14     return img_byte_arr
```

Code A.3 – Freezing Code Block

```
1 vae.requires_grad_(False)  
2 text_encoder.requires_grad_(False)
```